

ROBUST

CRISIS GOVERNANCE IN TURBULENT TIMES

Framework for studying societal intelligence

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1) Introduction

Robustness is a feature of adaptive conservatism. In between the overly conservative stance of resilience and the radically innovating strategy of agility, robust governance aims at adapting and innovating while preserving essential functions, goals, and values. The necessity to innovate and adapt comes from the context of the ROBUST project, working on providing both new theoretical frames and supporting data on governance in times of crisis.

What is essential to underline is that at this point, crises seem to be a new normal in public administration – thus fostering the need for robust tools for policy-makers and society at large, including experts and citizens. Taking into account the primary focus of this project on COVID-19 as a case study, it also appears clear such a crisis cannot be adequately managed within the limits of so-called policy silos.

ROBUST addresses this challenge by posing that robust politics and robust policies are predicated on three independent variables, namely: interactivity between multiple levels of governance; hybridity in or mixes of governance, democracy, and law; and the use of negotiated societal intelligence. This paper focuses on societal intelligence, reviewing existing literature and highlighting the current state of the art in the academic field. The review also supports the successive steps of the broader research project, by firstly conceptualizing societal intelligence and then hypothesizing conditions for creating societal intelligence in times of crisis.

A surprisingly wide array of academic disciplines contributes to the conceptualization of societal intelligence, including international public administration, crisis management, risk regulation, public relations, clinical neuroscience, social epistemology, public management, business strategy, philosophy, and environmental policy. The next paragraphs delve deeper into this conceptualization, followed by an outline of the methodology employed.

a) What is societal intelligence?

First, let's consider intelligence. This term usually refers to some sort of cognitive capacity. The Oxford Dictionary defines intelligence as “*the ability to learn, understand and think in a logical way about things; the ability to do this well*”.

When exploring additional academic sources on the term intelligence, authors underline features such as learning quickly and from experience, comprehending complex ideas, and adapting effectively to the environment for survival (Colom et al., 2010; Mulgan, 2018; Sternberg, 2012). In addition, when researching emotional intelligence Mayer (2004) includes in the definition of intelligence the “ability to reason validly about information” (p.4), thus both with and about information. When discussing collective wisdom, Andler (2012) defines intelligence as “the capacity to understand the world and to use this understanding in order to find in due time acceptable solutions to an unlimited variety of pressing problems [...]” (p.79). The work by Andler, underlining acceptable solutions and pressing problems, resonates with research on crisis governance. Time shortage, uncertainty, and conflicting values are indeed main features of decision-making in crisis evaluation and response (Deverell, 2010, 2022; Philipps et al., 2023).

The qualification “societal” in societal intelligence suggests that the learning experience takes place in a social environment with diverse and at times conflicting cognitive frames and experiences. The ROBUST project and WP5 endorse this societal perspective by focusing on the knowledge and experiences enunciated by policy-makers, experts, and citizens. We assume that they engage with three distinct types of knowledge that are all relevant to addressing contemporary crises in our society. These are political knowledge, i.e., knowledge about the political system, its institutions, processes, and actors; expert knowledge, i.e., scientific knowledge, clearly defined and aimed at predicting and controlling uncertainty; and lifeworld knowledge, i.e., tacit, local knowledge accumulated from everyday experience, including intuitions, assumptions, beliefs, and values (Hallin, 2023). These types of knowledge are not necessarily exclusively linked to a certain actor. In our view, societal intelligence would entail that citizens, politicians, and scientists are able to identify the nature, scope, and origin of scientific, lifeworld, and political knowledge. If citizens are able to identify the nature and scope of scientific and political knowledge, without doing science or doing politics, we could argue there is more societal intelligence. Likewise, if politicians and scientists could identify the nature and scope of lifeworld

knowledge, without going through the experiences themselves, we again could argue that there is more societal intelligence, If scientists could identify the nature and scope of political and lifeworld knowledge, there would be more societal intelligence.

Figure 1 illustrates that in order to analyze societal intelligence we must address how and where these different types of knowledge “meet” – or do not meet – to produce timely solutions in times of crisis. As underlined by Landemore (2012a), *cognitive diversity* matters when it comes to problem-solving, more than individual ability. Cognitive diversity is defined in her chapter as “the existence in a group of different interpretive and predictive models used by individuals to navigate the world” (pp.5-6). Servan-Schreiber and Larmanou (2023) provide a relevant illustration of this point in their chapter on crowd forecasting infectious disease outbreaks. At the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, they asked participants “How many WHO member states will report more than 1000 confirmed cases of COVID-19 before April 2020?”. The forecasting crowd included people with some form of medical background (70%) and some skilled prediction traders (23%). Results show that both kinds of expertise i.e., in infectious diseases or forecasting, were leading to similar performance. Even if most participants were weak forecasters, their errors canceled each other out. In this way, the aggregate crowd forecasts provided accurate predictions. The authors explain this through the Diversity theorem, arguing that “the size of a group’s error decreases [not only] when individual errors are smaller,” but also when “different people make different mistakes” (p.404). Thus a diversity of opinions and hence a diversity of errors makes a group more intelligent, capable of making more accurate predictions.

Accordingly, our framework assumes that each knowledge type embodies indeed a certain interpretative and predictive model. Thus, cognitive diversity is attained when these different knowledge types meet. Such knowledge exchange and development takes place in interfaces (Figure 1), which can be exemplified by stakeholder relations such as government-academia or public-private partnerships, where “complementary capabilities, competencies, and resources” align (Hallin, 2023).

Figure 1: Knowledge types and interfaces as knowledge exchange structures. Source: ROBUST project.

The work of Landemore and Elster on collective wisdom (2012) together with the most recent contribution on collective intelligence edited by Boucher et al. (2023) represent an essential read when it comes to the conceptualization of societal intelligence. While other authors have discussed useful notions such as organizational learning (Dahlmann & Roehrich, 2019); organizational intelligence and collective knowledge (De Angelis, 2013), collective wisdom and collective intelligence come closer to the core themes of the ROBUST project.

Landemore (2012a) considers wisdom as a wider-encompassing notion than intelligence. Collective wisdom is thus meant to cover both “wisdom of the crowds” phenomena, as well as more “classically centralized deliberative exchanges” (p.9). Moving to collective intelligence, in her research on public reforms Bourdon (2009) argues that “to address complex problems and uncertainty, governments need to improve their ability to tap the collective intelligence of society to extract knowledge and meaning [...]” (p.222). More recently, Boucher et al. (2023) have also employed the term collective intelligence in the context of democracy and governance, defining it as “the capacity of groups to outperform individuals in problem-solving, innovation, prediction, creativity, and other cognitive tasks”, resembling the interpretation of Hiltz and Turoff (1978). Finally, Andler (2012) posits that “a system exhibits collective intelligence insofar as there exists within the system fragments of world understanding that are exploited by the system in such a way as to produce in due time solutions to a large variety of pressing problems, including problems arising from the need to further world understanding”. These definitions underline important themes such as uncertainty, sense-making, innovation, and urgency which are discussed further in this review.

Taking into account these previous studies and the context of crisis governance of the ROBUST project, the following definition of societal intelligence has been elaborated:

Societal intelligence is the capacity to make decisions informed by different types of knowledge whose epistemology is identifiable by the actors involved.

b) Methodology

This literature review can be characterized as a narrative review. As the most common type of review, narrative reviews focus on generating understanding and have a wide-ranging scope.

This approach is suitable for the present research project for multiple reasons. Firstly, the ROBUST project, particularly WP3 to 5, aims at theory-building on the topic of robust crisis governance and its driving or blocking factors. Such an inductive approach requires flexibility regarding the boundaries of the subject of study (Bryman, 2012), which is enabled within the broader scope of a narrative review. In addition, as this review has had a central role in the conceptualization and operationalization of societal intelligence, it also mirrors a process of incremental discovery which also correlates to a narrative type of review. Finally, and related to the previous points, the number of diverse disciplines contributing to the goal of this literature review also necessitated adaptable boundaries to the subject of study. Disciplines and journals contributing relevant material to this research were indeed identified throughout the process, not a priori.

The aforementioned arguments also suggest why a systematic type of review was not deemed appropriate for this project. While systematic reviews have gained more and more ground in the latest years given their transparency and replicability, not all areas of literature or research questions let themselves to such an approach (Bryman, 2012). Especially in the case of research within the social sciences and qualitative methods, the selection and quality criteria embedded in systematic reviews might be problematic. It would for example be a complicated task to assess the inclusion or exclusion of an article based on its (qualitative) methodological quality. Moreover, as underlined in the previous paragraph, the goal of generating understanding clashes with a report-like review such as the systematic one.

Even though this review is not systematic in nature, it is still possible to elaborate on the process leading to the collection of the materials and their critical interpretation. First of all, the literature reviewed in this research was collected from online academic repositories such as JSTOR, Taylor & Francis Online, and the Wiley Online Library, in addition to the library of the University of Antwerp as a physical repository. These lead to the retrieval of peer-reviewed journal articles, book chapters, encyclopedia articles, and a more limited amount of grey literature (e.g., technical reports). This search was guided by the subject of study of WP5, which is societal intelligence in the context of crisis governance. Accordingly, keywords employed in the search were among others: organization knowledge, intelligence, information crisis, information processing crisis, and crisis learning. The results of these search terms were examined through their title and abstract

for relevance to the WP5 and the ROBUST project. Once relevance was acknowledged, literature referred to within those titles was also considered following a snowball sampling technique. All the relevant titles were successively added to the referencing software, where they were cataloged and categorized through their main themes.

Having outlined the methodology employed and the definition of societal intelligence, the next sections will elaborate on the main themes identified within the literature: information and knowledge as the building blocks of intelligence; the impact of turbulence on societal intelligence and the main challenges depicted in the literature, such as strategic use of knowledge and uncertainty; and lastly existing typologies of interfaces, spelling out what can be observed as societal intelligence on the ground.

2) Information and knowledge: building blocks of intelligence

The terms information and knowledge are often interchangeably used in the literature of reference, often without precision and or in combination with additional concepts. Throughout

this review, information and knowledge are understood conforming to the long-established perspective of Ackoff (1989), according to whom in any system there are four classes of inputs: data, information, knowledge, and intelligence (in De Angelis, 2013, pp.807-808). When raw data is structured, it transforms into information; when information is given meaning based on context, it becomes knowledge; finally, applying knowledge to a situation or problem constitutes intelligence. De Angelis (2013) explains that intelligence is the level where decisions are made, where the “human capacity to interpret, analyze, predict, and act” accomplishes that transformation of

knowledge into intelligence (p.808).

This understanding is acknowledged by other scholars, too. Hallin (2023) claims that information remains passive until “used by those with the knowledge needed to interpret and process them” (p.33). She also adds that knowledge creates a capability for intellectual activity, which echoes the definition of societal intelligence provided in this project. Naustdalslid (2011) also illustrates this understanding clearly in the title of his piece on climate change, mentioning “the challenge of translating scientific knowledge into action”. Similarly, Iyalomhe et al. (2013) argue that policies are developed through translating and applying knowledge. In a more recent piece, Philipps et al. (2021) also support the idea that information is at the base of making decisions. They argue that there is often not a clear link between the local events and experiences and the ones at the central level, which constitutes one of the main challenges of information supporting decision-making. Finally, Hallin (2023) also argues for an evolution from the knowledge society paradigm¹ to a collective intelligence society, taking into account developments in artificial intelligence (AI), too. While the ROBUST project does not directly focus on AI, it is relevant to highlight that the most recent research on intelligence within democracy and governance is also engaged with this topic.

Regarding the terminology of information and knowledge relevant to this research, further confusion is caused by the overlap among notions such as information processing, knowledge management, knowledge production, knowledge transfer, knowledge exchange, and knowledge utilization. All these terms in the literature often seem to refer to a similar set of practices. It is valuable to explore this overlap and clarify the implications for the ROBUST project, starting with information processing and moving to knowledge in all its nuances.

¹ Knowledge societies are defined as “societies in which people have the capabilities not just to acquire information but also to transform it into knowledge and understanding, which empowers them to enhance their livelihoods and contribute to the social and economic development of their societies” (UNESCO, 2015). Accessible at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000232563?posInSet=2&queryId=cfd98ca5-978b-42fc-a612-8dd8b1d3123a>

a) Information processing

Information processing is defined as the three steps of “information gathering, interpreting and transferring” (Dahlmann & Roehrich, 2019, p.1634). Through information flows, an organization can learn. And it is from such learning experiences that collaborative engagement can take place. While Dahlmann and Roehrich work at the level of private firms, up- and down-streams engagement and information transfer are undoubtedly relatable to the dynamics of a multi-level governance system. This “reciprocal transfer of information” is also an argument brought forward by Philipps et al. (2023), according to which this is needed to implement a “rapid and effective innovative response” (p.193). Analogously, Bourgon (2009) underlines the need for flexibility, information, and knowledge sharing. What she adds to this debate is that citizens and other actors beyond the government possess different views and valuable information that helps shape those innovative responses. The European Economic and Social Committee has confirmed this argument in its project summary report on the role of CSOs in the integration of migrants and refugees, underlining that based on their knowledge and expertise these organizations should be included in the design of integration policies (EESC, 2020). Furthermore, the report also highlights the pivotal function of these organizations in tackling information asymmetry and providing information and advice to migrants and refugees. One illustration is Open Migration², a multi-issue organization created by the Italian Coalition for Civil Liberties (CILD). This organization defines itself as an “informative project”, thus aiming to provide relevant knowledge and materials for competencies’ development on the migration issue.

The literature on information processing also widely discusses the topic of uncertainty. According to Dahlmann & Roehrich (2019), uncertainty is defined as “a lack of the appropriate amount and quality of information needed to perform tasks (p.1634). Thus, the more uncertainty, the more information needs to be gathered. The authors embed this definition within their discussion of the organizational information-processing theory (OIPT), whose goal is indeed to reduce uncertainty and manage equivocality for the final goal of superior performance. Uncertainty and equivocality are presented as the two components of information asymmetry. Philipps, Roehrich, and Kapletia (2023) further elaborate on this theme by applying it to situations of crisis, which is particularly relevant for the ROBUST project. They indeed argue that events such as COVID-19 are characterized by information asymmetry. In such a situation, the effective sharing of information, skills, and resources is crucial. Organizations would – according to the theory – start gathering more information first to solve uncertainty. This seems to be the strategy adopted by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the Financial Stability Board in 2009, with their report on “The financial crisis and information gaps” to the G20 finance ministers and central bank governors. This report – which was also followed by a conference³ – gathers recommendation points aiming at reducing information asymmetry and equivocality, and thus the uncertainty of the crisis. As an illustration, among the recommendations, there is a call to “improved collection and sharing of information [...] and the information exchange being considered for crisis management planning” or to “enhance the frequency and timeliness” of certain data. In addition, the IMF is also called to promote “timely and cross-country standardized and comparable government finance data”. The document of course also makes references to the limits of such data collection when it comes to financial information given its confidentiality.

This partially mirrors the limitations underlined by Philipps et al. (2023) in their work on responding to information asymmetry in the case of COVID-19. The authors argue that there is limited capacity to address uncertainty fully, and tackling equivocality – i.e., making sense of messy information – might be neglected altogether. In addition, while it was possible to provide an example for the financial crisis, this recent paper argues that there is a limited theoretical and empirical understanding of information asymmetry and how this is tackled by organizations in the case of a crisis such as COVID-19.

² <https://openmigration.org/en/>

³ <https://www.imf.org/external/np/seminars/eng/2010/infogaps/index.htm#prg>

b) Knowledge management

The recognition of different perspectives and the need to consider and include this diversity is also a theme in the literature on knowledge. Authors indeed underline that the framing of issues results from the promotion of certain types of knowledge and “dominant disciplinary framings” (Hoppe et al., 2013, p.290). In the example brought forward by these authors on climate change, this is illustrated through the geophysical sciences and economics – which represent the dominant disciplines. This also implies that other ones are marginalized, thus leading to an epistemological hierarchy of disciplines. Applying this to this research project, the question arises whether the same happened with COVID-19 and which types of knowledge and disciplines have been promoted, and which ones have been marginalized.

Types of knowledge are indeed a disputed subject in the literature within knowledge management, often revolving around the distinction between explicit and tacit knowledge. Bordum (2004) discusses the rise of tacit knowledge as a topic within the discipline in the context of companies’ strategies. His work includes a relevant definition of tacit knowledge as “personal, context-specific, and hard to formalize and communicate” (p.51). Thus, all our personal experiences and intuitions, our ideas and emotions, fall within tacit knowledge (see Polanyi, 1966). On the other hand, according to Platts and Yeung (2000), explicit knowledge can be transferred quickly and without financial burdens, through e.g., a presentation or an e-mail. Their argument is grounded in the idea that the Western world has taken a scientific and reductionist view of knowledge, therefore favoring and legitimizing explicit knowledge. They call this the “management approach” (p.349), in line with the New Public Management (NPM) stream focusing on performance standards, results, measurement, and monitoring.

This idea that knowledge can be easily transferred among individuals has been more recently reiterated by Putz and Brassel (2021), who contrast this positivist view with a more subjective one that acknowledges different types of knowledge. Gustafsson et al. (2017) support the connection of this dual debate to practice, underlining that it is essential to know how different types of knowledge contribute to change. The theoretical introduction to their research presents three models of knowledge production (Table 1): the classical linear model, where scientific findings have a direct translation in policies; the relational model, including concepts such as co-production; and the emergent model, which embeds a certain degree of unpredictability in the knowledge production and the dissolution of hierarchies between science and non-science. According to the authors, it is this third model that allows studying the engagement of such diverse perspectives coming from multiple actors and impacting decision-making.

Ideal models of knowledge production

<i>Linear model</i>	Scientists as separate from society; trustworthy, capable, and responsible for producing knowledge that leads society forward.
<i>Relational model</i>	Actors outside of science possess vital knowledge and play prominent roles in knowledge production. Experiences of practitioners are incorporated on an ongoing basis.
<i>Emergent model</i>	Absence of a central moderator or facilitator; actors and interfaces are unspecified. Knowledge that emerges from chaotic and unscripted interactions is sometimes weakly supported by evidence.

Table 1: Ideal models of knowledge production. Source: adapted from Gustafsson et al., 2017.

This last contribution already provides (theoretical) room for cohabitation between explicit and tacit knowledge. This is discussed more directly by De Angelis (2013), which defines knowledge management (KM) as “a set of practices aimed at the interaction between tacit and explicit knowledge” (p.808). Through such practices, an organization can act intelligently,

developing new competencies. The resonance of this concept comes also from practice, as e.g., the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) - which was active during the COVID-19 crisis in providing information and knowledge – has an “information and knowledge management” unit.

However, De Angelis (2013) also underlines that there is no agreed definition of what constitutes knowledge management in the field, and his description attempts to summarize the previous efforts. As mentioned above, this is not the only conceptual difficulty when it comes to this subject. The concept of knowledge management does indeed overlap with the one of knowledge exchange (KE), which is also prominent in the identified literature.

c) Knowledge exchange

Similarly to knowledge management, knowledge exchange is also defined as a process including the generation of knowledge (Putz & Brassel, 2021). Despite this parallel, research on knowledge exchange appears to have reached a higher consensus regarding definitions. Knowledge exchange is indeed defined as “processes of generating, sharing, and/or using knowledge through various methods appropriate to the context, purpose, and participants involved” (Fazey et al., 2012, p.19; Putz & Brassel, 2021, p.166). Both studies also mention knowledge co-production, grounded in the “participatory paradigm in science policy”, as labeled by Bäckstrand (2003). On the one hand, Putz and Brassel (2021) include it in their typology of knowledge exchange, under the cluster of “participatory knowledge development and use” (p.171). Conversely, Fazey et al. (2012) consider co-production a condition for more effective knowledge exchange. They indeed argue that such approaches emphasizing both co-production and adaptive learning would bring forward better outcomes in decision-making, both in effectiveness and durability.

Another compelling point of their research is the connection between knowledge exchange effectiveness and satisfaction, identity, and empowerment. Fazey et al. (2012) claim that the outcomes of processes of KE need to consider satisfaction to assess their effectiveness. Satisfaction is in this case associated at a deeper level with the validation (or lack thereof) of participants’ identity. This argument is further reinforced by the additional claim that KE is a process of empowerment (p.28): sharing knowledge is a conscious action that is entangled in the dynamics of power. Bringing co-production back into the discussion, the latter would according to the authors reduce the potential for conflict in such dynamics. This discussion is related in multiple ways to the goals of the ROBUST project. Firstly, transforming political conflict and tension is one of the features of robust politics. Moreover, robust policies are defined as the ones that allow for concerted collective action while sustaining and mobilizing political agency (D2.1). According to Bourgon (2009), it is indeed the solutions co-created by relevant parties that foster the possibility for such collective action.

Arguments on co-production are supported by Liu & Lin (2023) in their case study of deliberative policymaking during COVID-19 in Taiwan. Following some protests and success stories of open-government movements, the Taiwanese government funded in 2014 an open consultation platform called vTaiwan. Through this platform, the public is involved in four phases: brainstorming, preference expression, deliberation, and institution. The authors underline that letting people set the agenda on issues that concern them enhances how much they value the outcomes and ultimately the resilience of society in the face of the pandemic. The platform had indeed already allowed the establishment of some successful policies before COVID-19 peaked, such as the Long Distance Health Care Policy and the Long Distance Education. According to their research, this successively facilitated fast and co-created policy-making during COVID-19 on themes such as lockdowns and prioritization of emergency resources.

While co-production has been indeed on the rise within the literature (Bird & Lackey, 2014; Fazey et al., 2012; Gustafsson et al., 2017; Hoppe et al., 2013; Putz & Brassel, 2021; Van Enst et al., 2014), Bäckstrand (2003) challenges this view in her study on civic science for sustainability. The author does indeed question whether it is possible, or even desirable, to include citizens in processes of knowledge production, validation, and application (p.24). Scientific knowledge is indeed the realm of experts, focused on reducing uncertainty through scientific

methods. As Naustdalslid (2011) would put it, “science can develop scientific solutions” (p.249), which then are applied to societal problems. In this sense, as the direct recipient of the measures, society cannot be left out of these processes. Later in her article Bäckstrand (2003) additionally asks whether lay knowledge – ascribable to tacit knowledge – should be incorporated in risk assessment processes beyond the ones of risk management. This represents again a valid question. This tension is balanced by an argument put forward by Landmore (2012b), in her chapter on “Democratic reason”: when it comes to cognitive diversity, i.e., including different individual prediction models in decision-making, there are diminishing returns to adding more people after a certain threshold (p.271). This is also in line with the mechanisms of collective wisdom presented by the same author (Landmore, 2012a). She claims indeed that deliberative practices (such as coproduction) and aggregation procedures that “do not require actual communication or an exchange of views among the participants” (p.5) are both mechanisms of collective wisdom, a conceptualization that aligns with the different types of interface arrangements considered within societal intelligence (see section 4).

d) Intelligence as a social and epistemic activity

This brings us to the last point of this section, which clarifies the presence of the term epistemology in the definition of societal intelligence. Epistemology is a branch of philosophy that answers the question of *how we know what we know*. It deals with knowledge validity, its limits, and methods. Thus, different disciplines or groups possess different epistemologies and employ different methods to make sense of information and create knowledge.

Sternberg (2012) affirms that intelligence is a social activity, and as it involves the production of knowledge, too it is an epistemic one. Going back to the discussion on including society in risk assessment and processes of knowledge production and validation, multiple scholars argue for the need to incorporate additional factors into decisions other than scientific evidence, such as social interests and local knowledge (Bäckstrand, 2003; Naustdalslid, 2011; Thompson et al., 2021). This is also close to an argument by Putz and Brassel (2021), according to whom all the actors that are affected by a certain issue should be included in the discussion and to the cognitive diversity discussion by Landmore (2012a). Such reasoning is in line with the argument of post-normal science already brought forward by Funtowicz and Ravetz in 1993, which will be discussed later in this review.

Additional authors clarify why this inclusion is crucial from an epistemological point of view. If we consider the ways through which individuals get to know something, this is a finite list. Bruce (2008) discusses this in his piece “Making analysis more reliable: why epistemology matters to intelligence”. The principal ways of knowing are authority, habit of thought, rationalism, and empiricism (p.172). Science is also mentioned as a fifth way that combines both rationalism and empiricism. Relevant to this discussion is the first one, authority. In this case, there is a complete dependence on the source of information, which is more authoritative than who is communicating the knowledge. An illustration fitting to the ROBUST research project is a policymaker referring to expert knowledge and advice when communicating a new vaccination or restriction measure in the context of COVID-19. In this case and according to this typology by Bruce (2008), the citizen is experiencing authority as a way of knowing. The author underlines that the problem embedded in this is that the recipients cannot access how the knowledge was created in the first place and cannot see the logic behind it. In other words, the epistemology according to which this knowledge was produced is not available to the users. Andler (2012) also agrees with this point, arguing that what often “gets in the way” is that actors do not have access to the reasons of others, thus hindering the production of intelligent outcomes of labor. This is why this project’s definition of societal intelligence includes the wording “[...] decisions informed by different types of knowledge whose epistemology is identifiable by the actors involved”.

This choice and reasoning are further supported by arguments on consensus, structuredness of problems, and reciprocal understanding. Firstly, Van Enst et al. (2014) claim that if there is no consensus on what constitutes relevant norms and values, this will contribute to making problems even more unstructured – thus problems that lack a definite solution. This simultaneously creates the need for knowledge that is “credible, salient, and legitimate” (p.11).

Numerous scholars do indeed argue that the worlds of science and policy possess heterogeneous paradigms and there is a lack of reciprocal understanding between the two (Iyalomhe et al., 2013; Thompson et al., 2021). Having different epistemologies represents one of the barriers to knowledge exchange (Putz & Brassel, 2021).

Society is also added to this dual relation of misunderstanding, as Naustdalslid (2011) further claims that there is a lack of consistency between scientific knowledge and the tacit knowledge possessed by society, described as a mismatch between knowledge demand and knowledge supply by science in the work of Iyalomhe et al. (2013). He posits that this hampers effective action in the case of climate change, which is an interesting claim that could also be tested in other cases such as the ROBUST project and COVID-19. Hoppe et al. (2013) go indeed as far as to state that there is a problem of “global public epistemology” when it comes to such issues for which a global solution is necessary (p.295). According to these authors, it is important to consider that there exist competing models of knowledge-making in the world and that science is not universally accepted as authoritative. Dinesh (2023) presents a practical illustration of how they attempted to solve this mismatch and the need for a global solution in his chapter on smarter crowdsourcing in dealing with the COVID-19 pandemic. His case focuses on the “Smarter Crowdsourcing in the Age of Coronavirus” initiative, launched by various partners including TheGovLab⁴ at the beginning of the pandemic. Unlike common crowdsourcing efforts, Smarter Crowdsourcing is a methodology that not only brings a large number of people together to create knowledge – but also makes sure that expertise is diversified (both in discipline and language, country of origin) and brought together rapidly in times of crisis. This diverse expertise results in more innovative ideas, capable of tackling global problems. Dinesh also underlines that expertise, in this case, was also considered to be found in lived experience, thus matching our paper’s arguments on the importance of tacit knowledge and drawing from different types of knowledge. Experts could directly communicate with institutions and policymakers through the organized sessions, providing an opportunity for their diverse paradigms to come closer together and fill that gap between knowledge demand and supply.

The next sections will explicate the challenges to this approach to knowledge present in the literature, including themes such as strategic use of knowledge, uncertainty, sense-making, and learning.

3) Societal intelligence in turbulent times

While the literature presented in the previous section has emphasized the need to let different types of knowledge come into conversation with each other, other authors underline why this might not be such a straightforward goal to achieve. This brings us back to the crisis governance context of the ROBUST project. Turbulence has indeed a remarkable impact on key components of societal intelligence as presented in this paper. Firstly, crises are characterized by high information asymmetry (Philipps et al., 2023), potentially hampering knowledge development and exchange. Knowledge exchange and consequently societal intelligent decision-making does rely among others on the effective sharing of information (Ansell et al., 2020). In addition, Van Dooren and Noordegraaf (2020) underline that crisis conditions are not the ideal ones for the making of “good science”. Turbulent times are not ordinary, and this also implies that the demands on science change – in a way running “counter to how good science is practiced” (p.611-612). This is connected to previous discussions on epistemology and the mismatch between demand and supply of knowledge during crises.

The relationship between crisis and information, knowledge, and intelligence is thus clearly a theme in the literature – touching upon diverse topics. The main ones are discussed in the following sections, going through the strategic use of knowledge and monopolization of the public discourse, the handling of uncertainty caused by information asymmetry and equivocality, and lastly crisis-induced learning.

⁴ <https://thegovlab.org/>

a) Strategic use and production of knowledge

Van Enst et al. (2014) mention in their research both the handling of scientific uncertainties and the strategic use and production of knowledge. Starting with the latter, the authors clarify that this is a phenomenon taking place both on the side of policy and on the side of science. On the one hand, policymakers can indeed deliberately ignore certain bodies of knowledge, or use knowledge in a selected way. This also happens through advisory committees, which according to Backstrand (2003) are highly intertwined with political processes. Similarly, lyalomhe et al. (2013) claim that science's input into policies could also be easily distorted by the norms and institutional settings of policymaking. On the other hand, scientists could also selectively present knowledge, produce incomplete accounts, and thus retain the position of "problem owners", as defined by Naustdalslid (2011). According to this scholar, in an era where policymakers make an inflationary use of expert advice (Backstrand, 2003), scientists are in this unique position to "speak truth to power" (Naustdalslid, 2011, p.250). In this sense, Hoppe (2005) underlines that politics has paradoxically contributed to its own scientization.

However, there is also another side to this debate, and it touches upon consensus in the scientific community. Thompson et al. (2021) indeed claim that in the case of unsettled scientific debate, policymakers might ignore scientific input, which is usually deemed necessary to avoid policy failures (Baekkeskov & Oberg, 2017). A consequence and risk of such circumstances is that there is pressure on experts to appear consensual, especially if there is time pressure in terms of policymaking. Baekkeskov and Oberg (2017) call this the "rally to the flag", which would see scientists attempting to provide a timely response by presenting a unified front while hiding disagreements from the wider public. The authors also mention the media as contributing to this "rally" and biased selection of options by giving space in the news to experts who agree on a certain issue. The issue of exclusion of scientists who disagree with the dominant perspective is presented by Van Dooren and Noordegraaf (2020) as well in their research of "staging science" during COVID-19.

b) Uncertainty: challenging traditional science

However, in situations with high decision stakes and conflicting interests or implications, even (consensual) well-founded scientific knowledge might be rejected (Naustdalslid, 2011). This is where the theme of uncertainty comes in, which has a rather central role in the literature of reference. Illustrating this through the case of environmental policy issues, Putz and Brassel (2021) argue that traditional science has been challenged. Issues such as the environmental ones do indeed confront science with such conflicting values and deep uncertainties that multiple authors speak of post-normal science (Funtowics & Ravetz, 1993; Naustdalslid, 2011; Putz & Brassel, 2021). In their 1993 piece on "Science for the post-normal age", Funtowics and Ravetz claim that when facing this high level of systems uncertainties and decision stakes – which are their *x* and *y* – the applicable science is one including multiple legitimate perspectives, where it is not possible to retain full control and there is an assumption of unpredictability. The extension of the peer community in this framework includes everyone with a stake in the issue. To provide an example related to the migration crisis, the European Economic and Social Committee claims that migrants and refugees "should have a greater voice in the issues affecting their lives. It is important to talk with migrants, not about them" (EESC, 2020, p.4).

Thus, Funtowics and Ravetz add this problem-solving strategy of post-normal science to the other two parts of their framework: applied science, and professional consultancy (Table 2). These strategies are complementary to each other: scientific and expert knowledge stays relevant, and professional consultancy provides support, but an additional layer might be necessary when it comes to such deep epistemological uncertainty. On the one hand, Van Dooren and Noordegraaf (2020) claim that we are dependent on science for the reduction of uncertainty. On the other, Fazey et al. (2012) also add that over-relying on expert advice has paradoxically not reduced but increased the level of uncertainty. In this difficult balance, what we know from the COVID-19 case is that many European countries relied on professional consultancy – which makes the use of this framework still relevant today.

Newspapers such as POLITICO (Braun & De Villepin, 2021) and The Guardian (Jolly & Syal, 2020) have both published pieces on the role of consultants in supporting French and UK governments in delivering their public services, at a pace during the pandemic which caused some disbelief and shock by more conservative civil servants. POLITICO also highlights that indeed the UK, Spain, Germany, and Switzerland were also relying on consultancies and that this was not a new phenomenon at all. However, what seems unsettling is the increased frequency in recent years and the potential erosion of transparency and accountability. Given the challenges of turbulent times, consultancies supported governments working within time constraints and progressing much more rapidly on e.g., the test-and-trace system, medicines and protective equipment procurement, or more generally designing economic recovery plans. Section 4 will provide examples of interfaces also aiming at solving uncertainty at the epistemological level, by e.g., including multiple stakeholders.

<i>Level of uncertainty</i>	<i>Problem-solving strategy</i>
<i>Technical</i>	Applied science
<i>Methodological</i>	Professional consultancy
<i>Epistemological</i>	Post-normal science

Table 2: Uncertainty levels and solving strategies. Source: adapted from Funtowics and Ravetz, 1993.

c) Learning

When discussing information asymmetry and information-processing theory, Dahlmann and Roehrich (2019) also point out that information flows provide chances for organizational learning. Learning is another relevant issue when it comes to societal intelligence, especially in the context of crisis governance. Firstly, learning is present in multiple definitions of intelligence. As an illustration, Colom et al. (2010) include in their research on “human intelligence and brain networks” various descriptions of what intelligence is, including learning quickly and learning from experience. The value of experience is reiterated by Sternberg (2012) in his article on intelligence in “Dialogues in clinical neuroscience”.

Turning to political science, the work of Deverell (2010; 2022) is particularly relevant to the present research project. This author underlines the valuable input of organizational learning theory to explain the relationship between information, knowledge, organizational behavior, and change. According to the author, it is consolidated in this field that such change would concern both outcomes and states of knowledge – thus better understanding previous dynamics and successively acting accordingly. When it comes to policy change and learning, Hoppe (2005) provides a pessimistic argument by underlining that this change is “threatened by the political inclination to try and the political constraint not to fail – and consequently the political inability to learn” (p.212). Despite this more negative account, Deverell provides multiple perspectives on learning processes.

Two interesting pairs of concepts are discussed in both of Deverell’s publications (2010; 2022) in this respect. The first is the distinctness between single- and double-loop learning. Single-loop learning involves routine changes and is aimed at preserving consistency and thus the stability of fundamental norms, values, and principles. In the case of double-loop learning, the fundamental norms and policies of the organization would also undergo change. This would thus represent a more radical learning process. The second pair of concepts is inter- and intra-crisis learning. The former takes place after the crisis, learning from it and enacting changes that would make the organization prepared for the next one. The latter happens within the crisis, thus aiming at improving the management capacity when uncertainties and stakes are at their highest. Additional interesting points made by Deverell (2022) are that learning in an organization is a social activity, and it is also something that citizens would expect from policymakers and authorities in the aftermath of a crisis. Even more pertinent to the scope of ROBUST is the idea that “it takes a second crisis to mobilize attention to the underlying problems” (Kingdon, 2014 in Deverell, 2022). As ROBUST also includes a comparative element in its research objectives with

previous crises faced by the EU and its Member States, this perspective is a compatible lens for analysis. Crises do induce learning and Deverell highlights the need to research more about the relationship between organizational crisis management response and learning to build robust solutions.

To conclude this section, when discussing subjects such as policymakers balancing between efficiency and engagement, the strategic use of knowledge by science and politics, organizations learning and dealing with uncertainty, what still needs to be reframed is the role of citizens. Citizens cannot be indeed considered here just the recipients of these choices and actions, but an actor in themselves that needs to be included in a triangular interaction with science and policymakers (Backstrand, 2003; see Table 1). This author further adds that any framework aiming at studying the relationship between scientific expertise and public policy-making should include the public sphere. This is a goal of the ROBUST project, especially as societal intelligence is researched; it is also the reason why the definition of societal intelligence includes the words “[...] by different types of knowledge whose epistemology is identifiable [...]”. The next section will thus discuss the spaces where these interactions take place, i.e., interfaces. This will also serve as a more practical illustration of the theoretical debates from the literature presented until now in this review.

4) Societal intelligence on the ground: interfaces

Interfaces have been defined by multiple scholars, focusing on one or more features that exemplify the concept and interaction. The definition most cited in the literature is the one by van den Hove (2007), who wrote “A Rationale for science-policy Interfaces”. She defined science-policy interfaces as the “social processes which encompass relations between scientists and other actors in the policy process, and which allow for exchanges, co-evolution, and joint construction of knowledge with the aim of enriching decision-making” (p.815). Both Sarkki et al. (2015) and Van Enst et al. (2014) will later employ this definition in their research, with the former slightly adapting this conceptualization by adding that these processes could also enrich research beyond decision-making (p.506). Putz and Brassel (2021), in turn, talk about science-policy interaction and also define it according to the study by van den Hove from 2007. Iyalomhe et al. (2013) propose their own definition, describing the science-policy interface as a “complex multi-level system of control and of knowledge production among a group of actors engaged in knowing and managing crucial environmental issues” (p.371). Finally, and deviating the most from the other ones, Hoppe et al. (2013) define science-policy interactions from a macro-perspective as “ongoing co-productions between the scientization of politics and the politicization of science” (p.284).

Two elements are worth underlining regarding these definitions. Firstly, the production of knowledge as a goal of such a social process of interaction and engagement is constantly present. Secondly, the literature focuses exclusively on the interface between science and politics. While “other actors” are mentioned, the role foreseen for citizens is not clear in these conceptualizations. While this topic might be covered by other streams of scholarly output, such as citizen science (e.g., Madlen et al., 2023; Shruti et al., 2022), this reinforces the argument made above that citizens are mostly perceived in the literature as passive recipients of policies and/or expert advice, thus being excluded from accessing antecedent epistemologies by which the knowledge was created (Andler, 2012; Bruce, 2008).

Despite this, some authors have discussed the importance of democratic participation, science co-creation, and seeing science as a multi-party endeavor. For instance, Putz and Brassel (2021) argue that science is transforming into a multi-party dialogue and employ the post-normal science conceptualization by Funtowicz and Ravetz (1993) in their research. Similarly, Clar & Steurer (2016) claim that tools provided to support policy making, e.g., scientific advice in various forms, “must not ignore but build on the needs and capacities of target groups” (p.179). There is indeed agreement in the literature that actors outside of science possess valuable knowledge, which can complement professional expertise (Backstrand, 2003; Gustafsson et al., 2017) thus bridging the gap between what is happening locally and centrally (Philipps et al., 2023).

What further emerges from the literature on science-policy interfaces is that even these two worlds need bridging. Thompson et al. (2021) indeed underline that the effectiveness of this interface has been hampered by a lack of understanding between the paradigms and imperatives characterizing the two sides. Iyalomhe et al. (2013) define for this reason the interface between science and policy as ambiguous and they call for a revisiting of the relationship between science, end-users, and governance. They build up their point by discussing the need for translation of knowledge between science and policy. Putz and Brassel (2021) illustrate this gap between the two worlds by arguing that there are different expectations about how knowledge is to be exchanged, thus making KE a challenging process. This is supported by Clar and Steurer (2016) who state that knowledge does not transfer easily between science and policy-making. When giving examples of barriers to such knowledge exchange, Putz and Brassel (2021) mention the different epistemologies of science and policy-making – thus reiterating the previous argument about lack of the lack of understanding of each other's paradigms. The absence of interfaces is also presented in itself as a barrier to knowledge exchange, hence supporting the potential of such social processes.

Having critically presented the definitions, it is important to also present how interfaces could develop in practice. Authors have brought forward examples of civic science, communities of practice, and boundary organizations. These accounts will be here discussed together with the existing typologies of interfaces.

a) Civic science

Starting from civic science, Backstrand (2003) first presents a definition coming from the work of Clark and Illman (2001), according to whom civic science entails “the efforts by scientists to reach out to the public, communicate scientific results and contribute to scientific literacy” (p.28). She then gives her definition of civic science as participation and representation. The former highlights the need to increase public participation, thus placing civil society at the center of the scientific endeavor.

Examples presented by the author are consensus conferences, participatory technology assessments, citizen juries, and public hearings (p.28). By civic science as representation, it is meant solving the skewed representation in the current production of science, e.g., including marginalized groups. An interesting point made by Backstrand (2003) is that democratic participation in science is mainly taking place at the domestic level and is more limited as far as e.g., scientific assessment is concerned. With its consortium of partners, the ROBUST project could corroborate this in its analysis of societal intelligence.

b) Communities of practice

Moving to communities of practice, these are referred to by Iyalomhe et al. (2013) as activities taking place in a certain social and historical context that structures the engagement of participants. Wenger et al. (2002) define this term as “a group of people who share a concern, a set of problems, or a passion about a subject matter, and who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this by interacting on an ongoing basis” (p.371 in Iyalomhe et al.,2013).

Such a community has the potential to allow interactions between different paradigms and thus knowledge types. In addition, the authors underline that in this context the participants also negotiate how useful and relevant the jointly accepted knowledge is. Boucher et al. (2023) list communities of practice as a method to achieve one of the core functions of collective intelligence, i.e., sense-making, learning, generating memory and wisdom (Table 3).

Core functions of collective intelligence

Observing or gathering data

Modeling and predicting

Generating options

Filtering, deliberating, deciding

Implementing

Learning by making sense, remembering, synthesizing into wisdom

Table 3: Core functions of collective intelligence. Source: Boucher et al., 2023.

The creation of jointly accepted knowledge is indeed among the potential goals of these activities, together with joint problem-solving and mutual learning. Hallin (2023) claims indeed that communities of practice in societies are illustrations of ways through which collective tacit knowledge is formed. Iyalomhe et al. (2013) also underline that such activities can take place within more formal organizations, such as a research project. ROBUST is an example thereof, bringing together scholars from different EU countries and collecting their insights based on both explicit and tacit knowledge. Horizon has however supported multiple projects working on crisis management and governance through its funding schemes. Illustrations are the LEGITIMULT⁵ project, on legitimate crisis governance in multilevel systems (Horizon Europe program) and the TransCrisis⁶ on EU transboundary crisis management capacities (Horizon 2020).

c) Boundary organizations

Finally, Clar and Steurer (2016) and Hoppe (2005, 2013) have researched boundary organizations. Clar and Steurer (2016) maintain that the goal of boundary organizations is to facilitate two-way communication between science and policymaking. This can also be referred to as “knowledge brokerage” (p.172). The authors also illustrate services provided by such an organization to reach that goal, such as policy analyses and evaluations, compilations of scientific data, standardized decision support tools, networking and consulting services, and public awareness activities.

Additional examples are provided by Hoppe et al. (2013) under what they call “boundary objects”: e.g., indicator systems, econometric models, and report series. The latter research further defines what is included in boundary work, which according to them entails not only the quality assessment of scientific research but also e.g., the design of innovative policy instruments or the evaluation of policy impacts. According to previous research by Hoppe (2005), boundary work leads to the achievement of cognitive authority. Hoppe et al. (2013) also provide an example at the EU level of a boundary organization: the European Environmental Agency (EEA). Relating this to the crises analyzed by the ROBUST project, other EU decentralized agencies are relevant to our project as boundary organizations supporting EU crisis management. The European Banking Authority (EBA) was indeed set up in 2011 to support the management of the financial crisis. Similarly, the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (FRONTEX) was established in 2016⁷ following peak waves of migration in the European continent. While there is variety in the formal powers possessed by these bodies, they can be defined as interfaces between experts, citizens, and politicians where knowledge exchange can be facilitated and societal intelligence created.

d) Typologies: science-policy engagement, knowledge exchange, boundary arrangements

As regards typologies of interfaces, the following will describe the work of Thompson et al. (2021) categorizing science-policy engagement, of Putz and Brassel (2021) constructing a typology of knowledge exchange, and of Hoppe (2005) building models of boundary arrangements. First, Thompson et al. (2021) categorize science-policy engagement into three types based on the previous research of Cullen et al. (2001) and van Enst et al. (2014). Their categorization (Table 4) thus includes engagement as purchaser provider (I), collaborative (IIa), participatory knowledge development (IIb), co-generative (IIc), and boundary organization (III). Related to the debates recognized until now in this review, the participatory knowledge development and the co-generative categories of science-policy engagement possess interesting features that could support the bridging between the two worlds, such as scientists partaking as

⁵ <https://legitimult.eu/>

⁶ <https://www.lse.ac.uk/accounting/carr/research/TransCrisis/transcrisis>

⁷ The Regulation (EU) 2016/1624 founding this agency repealed the Council Regulation (EC) 2007/2004, which had set up the European Agency for the Management of Operational Cooperation at the External Borders of the Member States of the European Union. FRONTEX mandate has successively been amended in 2019 (Regulation (EU) 1019/1896).

mere participants and not initiators (IIb) or scientists working with policy to identify knowledge needs (IIc).

Models of engagement

I	Purchaser provider
IIa	Collaborative
IIb	Participatory knowledge development
IIc	Co-generative
III	Boundary organization

Table 4: models of science-policy engagement. Source: Thompson et al., 2021.

In terms of knowledge exchange, Putz and Brassel (2021) present a five elements typology: knowledge transfer, knowledge transfer support, knowledge exchange, knowledge exchange support, and participatory knowledge development and use (Table 5). In the categories including “support”, this implies the support by boundary organizations or knowledge advocates. Relevant to this research project is category 5.1, denominated “coproduction of knowledge through participation”.

<i>Typology of knowledge exchange</i>	<i>Examples of subtypes</i>
1. <i>Knowledge transfer</i>	Knowledge transfer as a result of knowledge demand
2. <i>Knowledge transfer support</i>	Direct or indirect knowledge transfer supported by boundary organizations
3. <i>Knowledge exchange</i>	Knowledge exchange as coproduction of knowledge
4. <i>Knowledge exchange support</i>	Direct or indirect knowledge exchange supported by boundary organizations
5. <i>Participatory knowledge development and use</i>	Coproduction of knowledge through participation

Table 5: Typology of knowledge exchange. Source: Putz and Brassel, 2021.

Lastly, Hoppe (2005) presents eight models of boundary arrangements (Table 6). These are based on two axes: whether there is primacy of science or politics, and whether there is a convergent or divergent logic between the science and political worlds. From this, derive the enlightenment, the technocracy, the bureaucracy, and the engineering model. The first two imply primacy for science, with technocracy embodying a convergent logic, i.e., experts holding power. The second two imply primacy for politics, with engineering embodying a convergent logic, i.e., politicians retaining the power and assigning detailed tasks to scientists as engineers. Hoppe (2005) also adds models based on advocacy (dispositional and adversarial) and learning (pure learning and coping).

Close to the research goals of this project, the dispositional model sees science advisors and policy-makers both as influencing the political discourse, while science produces boundary objects as the ones illustrated above. The coping model represents on the other hand the struggle of politicians presented in the section on learning, where they experience this balancing exercise between the need to change and the inclination to try, and the constraint not to fail – thus ultimately being unable to learn.

	<i>Convergent logic</i>	<i>Divergent logic</i>	<i>Advocacy</i>	<i>Learning</i>
<i>Primacy of science</i>	Technocracy	Enlightenment	Dispositional	Pure learning
<i>Primacy of politics</i>	Engineering	Bureaucracy	Adversarial	Coping

Table 6: Models of boundary arrangements. Source: adapted from Hoppe, 2005.

e) Analyzing societal intelligence: application to the ROBUST project

To summarize, it is clear there is a variety of valid approaches through which the ROBUST project could proceed to analyze societal intelligence. As an illustration, such an informed decision-making capacity could indeed be developed through civic science, intended as public participation (e.g., public hearings) or representation (e.g., including marginalized groups in scientific assessment). Communities of practice represent another option, having as an objective the creation of jointly accepted knowledge, joint problem-solving, and mutual learning. An illustration is the COVID-19 Health Financing Resiliency Program Community of Practice, hosted by the Collaboration for Development (C4D) platform of the World Bank. In this online space, practitioners from different backgrounds and country of origin are encouraged to share ideas and needs. At the same time, boundary organizations – such as the EU decentralized agencies mentioned above – could provide knowledge brokerage through e.g., policy analyses, consulting services, and networking opportunities.

In all these examples, the production of knowledge is central. There is also a call in the literature to revisit the relationship between science, governance, and end users (Figure 1). This goal aligns with the need to expand this branch of the literature beyond the limited focus on the science-policy interface, analyzing the experts-citizens and the citizens-policy-makers interfaces, too. The typology that allows ROBUST to undertake such a task is the one of *knowledge exchange* (Table 5) as conceptualized by Putz and Brassel (2021). Ranging from knowledge transfer to participatory knowledge development and use, this typology offers the possibility to identify different forms of knowledge exchange and production and ultimately the creation of societal intelligence through diverse configurations. These types consider elements such as knowledge supply and demand, knowledge brokerage or support by boundary organizations, as well as participatory practices, including learning. This also coincides with our understanding that societal intelligence is not only developed through forms of direct participation of the public but also via more or less tight collaborations, direct or indirect transfers, and the intermediary support of diverse actors. The following table (Table 7) presents the typology with all the subtypes proposed by its authors.

<i>Typology of knowledge exchange</i>	<i>Subtypes</i>
<i>1. Knowledge transfer</i>	1.1 Knowledge transfer as a result of knowledge demand 1.2 Direct knowledge transfer from a supply perspective 1.3 Indirect knowledge transfer from a supply perspective
<i>2. Knowledge transfer support</i>	2.1 Direct knowledge transfer supported by boundary organizations 2.2 Indirect knowledge transfer supported by boundary organizations 2.3 Knowledge transfer supported by knowledge advocates 2.4 Awareness-raising activities
<i>3. Knowledge exchange</i>	3.1 Knowledge exchange as coproduction of knowledge 3.2 Knowledge exchange by tight collaboration 3.3 Knowledge exchange by loose collaboration
<i>4. Knowledge exchange support</i>	4.1 Direct knowledge exchange supported by boundary organizations 4.2 Indirect knowledge exchange supported by boundary organizations 4.3 Knowledge exchange supported by knowledge advocates
<i>5. Participatory knowledge development and use</i>	5.1. Coproduction of knowledge through participation 5.2 Retrieval of knowledge through participation 5.3 Learning through participation 5.4 Participation to acquire new input 5.5. Participation in knowledge evaluation

Table 7: Typology of knowledge exchange with subtypes. Source: Putz and Brassel, 2021.

This typology will be employed to categorize and identify trends within the data collected on societal intelligence both at the national and the European level of governance within WP5. This is an important step for multiple reasons. Firstly, it will allow us to determine which type of knowledge exchange is commonly used on a certain interface and level of governance. Secondly, it will be possible to acknowledge changes or sequences in types at the occurrence of turbulence. Triangulating these observations with interviews and additional documents, the final goal will be to assess whether such exchanges lead to the creation of societal intelligence. This research ultimately contributes to filling gaps established in the literature. Van Enst et al. (2014) mention that although the challenges to the science-policy interface have been identified, which configuration or typology of interface would solve them is still unknown. The conditions under which the typologies previously described take place have also not been researched systematically, and Hoppe et al. (2013) underline the need for quality data on boundary work, too – including necessary and sufficient conditions. Hoppe (2005) also suggests that future research could also look not only into the circumstances leading a certain model of an interface to take place but also at the circumstances of its decline and at whether there are sequences or pairings of such models over time.

In addition to relevant typologies and avenues for further research, the body of literature here presented provides valuable assumptions that can guide the efforts of data collection and analysis. Societal intelligence as a capacity seems indeed to be connected to certain conditions, which our analysis could later evaluate as potentially necessary and/or sufficient. For example, authors underline that expanding the peer community to involve more legitimate perspectives or including additional factors in risk assessment are favorable steps. The same goes for the interaction between tacit and explicit knowledge, and learning from experience. Considering knowledge as empowering would also point to the creation of societal intelligence. Finally, the literature also warns against two potential obstacles. On the one hand, different epistemologies can challenge knowledge exchange, a hypothesis already discussed in section 2d. On the other, public expert advice could negatively impact deliberation and the number of policy alternatives considered.

5) Conclusion

This literature review had the goal of providing an overview of the existing scholarly output supporting the definition and the research of the independent variable of societal intelligence part of the ROBUST research project. Touching upon themes such as information, knowledge and its strategic use and production, uncertainty, learning, and interfaces, the term societal intelligence is here defined as the “capacity to make decisions informed by different types of knowledge whose epistemology is identifiable by the actors involved”. Arguments from a diverse set of disciplines have led to this conceptualization of societal intelligence. Intelligence does indeed deal with learning, adapting to the environment, and reasoning validly about information. Societal points out which type of information and knowledge intelligence is built on and reasons about. It also clarifies where the learning experience takes place and against which environment adaptation needs to occur.

Turning now to a summary of the main points of this review, intelligence is in this project considered the fourth and last of the inputs composing any system, together with data, information, and knowledge. It is in fact when knowledge is applied to a situation or problem that it constitutes intelligence. Thus, intelligence is a feature at the level of decision-making that can have an impact on the production of robust policies and robust politics.

Three main theoretical perspectives on information and knowledge are present in the literature. The first one is information processing, underlining that it is through information flows that organizations can learn. The second one is denominated knowledge management. Within this scholarly work, the difference between explicit and tacit knowledge is highlighted, together with the need to make the two interact to achieve innovative responses. The third, knowledge exchange

(KE), focuses on knowledge as empowerment, knowledge co-production, and reduction of conflict. One of the main arguments in KE is the need to include society and generally additional factors (i.e., different types of knowledge) when it comes to the assessment of risk and decision-making processes. All parties affected by the decision are indeed directly legitimate parts of these processes. This is connected to the presence of the term epistemology in the definition of societal intelligence. All affected actors should not only be able to access the information (thus enabling information flows as a result of transparency) but also find the knowledge employed in the decision-making to be credible, salient, and legitimate.

The literature also touches upon challenges regarding information, knowledge, and learning. First of all, knowledge exchange is hindered by the different paradigms between the worlds of policy and science. Furthering this gap is the strategic use of knowledge, by both scientists and policy-makers. Especially in turbulent times, there is pressure to appear consensual and to “rally to the flag”. The handling of uncertainty is another relevant theme. Information processing has in itself the goal of reducing uncertainty, which is a component of information asymmetry together with equivocality. Reliance on expert advice is also a strategy employed to reduce uncertainty. However, over-relying on them also has the paradoxically opposite effect of increasing uncertainty. In such times, where the uncertainty goes as deep as that epistemological level, traditional science is challenged, and post-normal science is a useful lens. In this context, institutions and policy-makers are expected to learn from experience and do it quickly.

Finally, moving to a more practical application of the concepts reviewed, the literature on interfaces provides wide coverage of the science-policy nexus. Authors provide typologies of science-policy engagement, knowledge exchange, and boundary arrangements. Common to all is the construction of knowledge as a goal, the value of local knowledge as complementing scientific expertise, co-creation, and science as a multi-party endeavor.

This body of scholarly output reviewed also provides suggestions for further research, as authors highlight the gaps in their disciplines. Firstly, it is not clear how organizations address information asymmetry and information processing throughout a crisis. Interfaces such as boundary organizations or communities of practice might be involved in such processes, but the conditions under which interfaces take place are also not systematically researched. There is indeed no data on quality boundary work and what are the necessary and/or sufficient conditions for a certain interface to take place, to decline, to be substituted by another one, or by a certain configuration of interfaces. Thus, there is a need to look into these dynamics.

Furthermore, while there is consensus that traditional science is challenged by turbulence and that there are multiple legitimate perspectives to be included, how citizens can participate in the production, validation, and application of scientific knowledge is still to be understood. Within the post-normal science understanding, it is also necessary to develop guidelines for the organization of knowledge processes. In this context, it is also valuable to identify knowledge gatekeepers in different settings. Given the impact this has on knowledge exchange and thus on learning, it could also bring further light on why some individuals and organizations learn and reform and others do not. There is indeed a lack of empirical studies presenting examples of both inter and intra-crisis learning. Lastly, given the pressure to appear consensual, further research could also study the impact of experts on the range of policy options considered.

To conclude, this paragraph will mention the limitations of the current deliverable and what implications these debates and arguments have on the operationalization of societal intelligence. One important point to underline here is that many academic works included in this review focus on environmental policy, environmental issues, and climate change. While these perspectives do resonate with the understanding of the crisis and challenges brought about by COVID-19, these theoretical premises need to be corroborated by empirical data and analysis. In addition, this review covers only certain streams of literature. Other relevant frameworks and findings e.g., trust, network governance, and risk management will be included in future deliverables to confirm and control findings on societal intelligence and impact on robustness.

What do these scholarly debates thus mean for societal intelligence and how the latter will be studied in the context of the ROBUST project? The previous section has already discussed some assumptions coming from the literature which will guide WP5 in the data collection and

analysis, together with the relevant typology of knowledge exchange. In practice, this all translates into more specific questions within themes such as the implementation of crisis response, the adaptation and innovation capacity during crises, and the experiences and challenges of different actors. For example, we will enquire about the involvement of diverse actors to overcome shortcomings due to turbulence. This will support the identification of different types of knowledge and knowledge exchange possibly involved. Central to this work package will also be questions focusing on handling information and fighting uncertainty in times of crisis, highlighting a certain risk perception from the organization and whether, again, different types of knowledge were taken into account to solve such information asymmetry and equivocality. In the case of politicians and administrators at the national, regional, or local level, this also implies gathering data on what kind of expertise they sought support from. In addition, these actors and public health agencies' personnel will also receive questions regarding the communication of knowledge and potential strategies changes that took place during the COVID-19 timeline. Moreover, and relevant to knowledge brokerage, data will be collected on the role of civil society organizations in helping make sense of information. Finally, the evolution of the role of science and expert knowledge in times of crisis will be enquired upon given the potential challenges posed by the strategic use of knowledge and limitation in policy alternatives and deliberation.

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